

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE FORMATION OF AN INNOVATIVE ECONOMY IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This research work provides a comprehensive analysis of the role of digital technologies in the development of the innovative economy in Uzbekistan and the population's understanding of digital technologies in shaping the innovative economy. Based on statistical data for 2020-2023, surveys conducted in 5 regions (1,000 respondents), and interviews with IT specialists, the level of digital literacy, the state of the education system, and the readiness of enterprises for digital transformation were studied. The results of the study show that while digital literacy among 18-25-year-olds is 68%, this indicator drops to 12% among those aged 60+. Sharp differences between rural and urban areas, age groups, and levels of education are identified. The article proposes measures to reduce the digital divide, reform the education system, and encourage enterprises. The research results include practical recommendations that can be used in the implementation of the "Digital Uzbekistan 2030" strategy. The article analyzes the current state, prospects and obstacles to the formation of an innovative economy in Uzbekistan based on statistical data. The impact of digitalization on economic growth, current problems and proposals for their elimination are presented.

Keywords: digital economy, innovative development, artificial intelligence, Uzbekistan, statistical analysis.

Аннотация. В данной исследовательской работе представлен комплексный анализ роли цифровых технологий в развитии инновационной экономики в Узбекистане и понимания населением цифровых технологий в формировании инновационной экономики. На основе статистических данных за 2020-2023 годы, опросов, проведенных в 5 регионах (1000 респондентов), и интервью с IT-специалистами изучены уровень цифровой грамотности, состояние системы образования и готовность предприятий к цифровой трансформации. Результаты исследования показывают, что если среди 18-25-летних уровень цифровой грамотности составляет 68%, то среди лиц в возрасте 60+ этот показатель снижается до 12%. Выявлены резкие различия между сельской и городской местностью, возрастными группами и уровнями образования. В статье предлагаются меры по сокращению цифрового неравенства, реформированию системы образования и стимулированию предприятий. Результаты исследования включают практические рекомендации, которые могут быть использованы при реализации стратегии «Цифровой Узбекистан 2030». В статье на основе статистических данных анализируется современное состояние, перспективы и препятствия на пути формирования инновационной экономики в Узбекистане. Представлены влияние цифровизации на экономический рост, текущие проблемы и предложения по их устранению.

Ключевые слова: цифровая экономика, инновационное развитие, искусственный интеллект, Узбекистан, статистический анализ.

Introduction. In recent years, Uzbekistan has been carrying out comprehensive reforms to develop the digital economy. The "Digital Uzbekistan 2030" strategy, through the introduction of e-government systems, artificial intelligence and cloud technologies, is in the process of transitioning the country to an innovation system. The level of use and understanding of digital technologies by the population is a decisive factor in the development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan. According to the "Digital Uzbekistan 2030" strategy, it is planned that by 2025 80% of the population will use digital services. The country faces a number of problems on the way to an innovation system:

Technological gap (uneven development of Internet infrastructure between urban and rural areas);

Lack of qualified personnel (emigration of IT specialists abroad - the phenomenon of "brain drain");

Inadequate cybersecurity and data protection laws.

Relevance of the research: The introduction of digital technologies is one of the main directions of creating an innovative economy for Uzbekistan.

The main purpose of the article is to statistically study the impact of digital technologies on the innovative economy in Uzbekistan and determine the following:

The research was conducted based on the following methods:

1. **Statistical analysis** (official data for 2020-2023)
2. **Questionnaires** (1,000 respondents in 5 regions)
3. **Expert assessment method** (interviews with 20 IT specialists)

Digital Literacy Level of the Population⁶⁴

Demographic group	Literacy rate (%)	Main problems
18-25 years old	68%	Lack of practical knowledge
26-40 years old	54%	Lack of time
41-60 years old	32%	Technophobia
60+ years old	12%	Difficulty adapting

2. Situation in Educational Institutions

- Only 45% of higher education institutions have modern digital programs
- The level of training in digital technologies in vocational colleges is 28%

3. Situation in Enterprises

- 60% of small and medium-sized businesses do not actively use digital technologies
- Only 15% of enterprises have special digital transformation departments

Statistical Analysis and Issues

1. State of Digital Infrastructure⁶⁵

Indicator	2020	2023
Internet users (% population)	67%	75%
Mobile internet speed (Mbps)	12.4	25.1
5G network coverage	0%	15% (Tashkent)

One of the main problems is the low quality of the Internet in rural areas (speed below 10 Mbps).

2. Investments and Jobs in the IT Sector

- Investments in the IT sector in 2023: 320 million (in 2020 - 120 million).
- However, 40% of IT specialists work abroad (Source: IT Park reports).

3. Digital Government (E-Government) System

- 80% of government services are provided electronically;
- However, only 35% of the population actively uses these services (Stat.uz, 2023).

Solutions and Proposals

1. Infrastructure Development

- Introduction of the 5G network to all regional centers (achieving 80% coverage by 2030);
- Expansion of fiber-optic internet in rural areas.

⁶⁴ Source: Ministry of Information Technologies of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2023)

⁶⁵ Source: Ministry of Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2024)

2. Reform of the Personnel Training System

In the field of education:

- Introduction of the subject "Digital Literacy" to all levels of education
- Expansion of teacher retraining programs
- Introduction of programming and artificial intelligence subjects in schools;
- Allocating international grants to IT universities.

In the economy:

- Provision of tax incentives to enterprises for the introduction of digital technologies
- Expansion of state grants for digital transformation

Legal Reforms

- Update of the Cybercrime Law (introduction of modern amendments to the AINI Code);
- Expansion of start-up financing programs.

Summary

Digital technologies play an important role in shaping an innovative economy in Uzbekistan. However, efficiency can be increased by improving infrastructure, qualified personnel and the legal framework, as well as strengthening international cooperation.

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